

Aluminium Chloride Catalyzed Electrophilic Substitution on 6-Substituted Resorcinol

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Aluminium chloride catalyzed substitution on resorcinol takes place at 2-position or 4-position accordingly, as the third substituent already present at 6-position on the nucleus, is an acyl or alkyl group respectively.

The main product of condensation when a β -ketoester is condensed with resacetophenone is a 5-hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin derivative¹, the point of attack being the otherwise inaccessible 2-position. Shah *et al.*² believe that this reactivity of the 2-position is due to some specific action of aluminium chloride itself, with POCl_3 the attack taking place at 4-position³. The specific action of aluminium chloride which orients the entering group on 2-position of resorcinol seems to be dependent upon the third substituent already present on the benzene nucleus. A negative group at 6-position usually directs the entering group at sterically less favourable 2-position, ortho to both the hydroxyl groups of resorcinol. When the third substituent is an alkyl group the condensation with AlCl_3 has been found to take place at the usual free 4-position of resorcinol⁴.

The specific action of aluminium chloride has also been observed in case of substitution of coumarins obtained from resorcinol. Although the 6- and 8-positions of 7-acetoxycoumarin are of similar reactivity⁵, the usual product of Fries rearrangements is 8-acetyl derivative⁶. Here the 3 : 4-unsaturated bond conjugated with $> \text{C} = \text{O}$ of pyrone, function as a negative group, which facilitate the entry of acyl group⁷ at the position ortho to both the oxygen atoms. But as soon as the 3 : 4-bond of coumarin is reduced, the substitution due to Fries rearrangement takes place at 6-position⁸ *viz.*, 7-acetoxy-3 : 4-dihydrocoumarin furnishes 7-hydroxy-6-acetyl-3 : 4-dihydrocoumarin as the only isolable product.

Further evidence in support of the above view point is presented as follows. Resacetophenone and acrylonitrile were condensed in presence of aluminium chloride (3.5 mole) and dry hydrogen chloride gas at 145–50° when a product melting at 129° was obtained.

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This was found to be different from 6-acetyldihydroumbelliferone I⁸ by mixed melting point determination. The substitution obviously took place at 2-position, and subsequent cyclization with one of the *o*-hydroxy groups resulted in either II or III. Since the hydroxy group at 1-position of resacetophenone is protected due to hydrogen bonding with *o*-acetyl group the product formed was, as expected, 5-hydroxy-3,4-dihydro-6-acetylcoumarin II (*vide infra*). But as soon as the acetyl group of resacetophenone is reduced to ethyl group,

the product of reaction under similar condition with acrylonitrile is identical with 6-ethyl-7-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin⁹, the substitution being at the usual 4-position of resacetophenone.

6-Acetyl-5-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin (II) on dehydrogenation with Pd-C in diphenyl oxide gives 5-hydroxy-6-acetylcoumarin (IV) (m.p. 165°) which is identical with Fries rearrangement product of 5-acetoxycoumarin as found by mixed melting point determination.

Although the two positions 6- and 8- are identical with respect to reactivity⁵ in electrophilic substitution reaction, the substitution takes place at 6-position only. But when the 6-position is already occupied by an ethyl group the Fries rearrangement takes place smoothly at 8-position.

5-Acetoxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin also produces II, when heated with 3.5 mole aluminium chloride at 190°. Thus orientation of Fries rearrangement of 5-acetoxycoumarin is not dependent on whether the pyrone ring is reduced or not, in contrast to the orientation of Fries rearrangement of 7-acetoxycoumarin.

That the relative positions of hydroxy and acetyl groups in II and IV are ortho to each other is indicated by ferric chloride test, when a cherryred colouration takes place⁹ whereas VII with ferric chloride gives a greenish yellow colour. The ketonic I.R. band of VII is at 1690 cm^{-1} whereas those of II and IV are at 1630 cm^{-1} indicating a band shift towards lower frequency due to hydrogen bonding.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected. The compounds were repeatedly crystallised until constant melting points and single spots on TLC were obtained.

6-Acetyl-5-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin II: Finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (33.6 g, 0.25 mole) was added slowly to the mixture of resacetophenone (15.8 g, 0.1 mole), acrylonitrile (21.2 g, 0.4 mole) and ether (200 ml.), which was stirred vigorously at 10–15°. Dry hydrogen chloride was bubbled through, when a clear solution was obtained. Ether was slowly removed first at 50–60° and later at 100° in an oil-bath when an yellowish slurry resulted. The temperature was then raised gradually upto 145–50°; heating was continued, maintaining the current of hydrogen chloride throughout the whole reaction period. After 3–4 hrs. whole mass became a glassy solid. The mixture was decomposed by boiling with 250 ml. 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether and ethereal layer was dried over sodium sulphate. The residue, after removal of solvent, on sublimation

(205–10°/1 mm) gave 16 g. of product which on crystallisation from ethanol yielded 12.6 g. (60%) of 6-acetyl-5-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin m.p. 129° (Found : C, 63.92; H, 4.92. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires : C, 64.07; H, 4.89). The I.R. spectrum showed bands at 1775 cm^{-1} (lactone) and at 1630 cm^{-1} (hydrogen bonded ketone).

The above compound (II) was also prepared by the Fries rearrangement of 5-acetoxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin¹⁰ (0.8 g, 0.004 mole) by heating at 180–190° with intimately mixed anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.9 g, .014 mole). The product was decomposed with HCl (1 : 1) and extracted with ether and ethylacetate. The solvent after removal gave a solid (0.8 g.) which on purification by sublimation (200°/1 mm) yielded 0.6 g. of product m.p. 127°, mixed m.p., with II was undiminished.

6-Acetyl-5-hydroxycoumarin IV : A mixture of 6-acetyl-5-hydroxy-3,4-dihydrocoumarin (1 g.), diphenyl oxide (20 ml.), Pd-C 10% (0.6 g.) was refluxed for 6 hr. Catalyst was removed by filtration from hot solution and solvent on evaporation under reduced pressure yielded a solid which on crystallisation from methanol gave 0.8 g. of 6-acetyl-5-hydroxycoumarin IV, m.p. 165° (Found : C, 64.52; H, 3.84. $C_{11}H_8O_4$ requires : C, 64.70; H, 3.95). The I.R. spectrum showed bands at 1727 cm^{-1} (coumarin) and at 1630 cm^{-1} (hydrogen bonded ketone).

The above compound IV was also prepared by the Fries rearrangement of 5-acetoxycoumarin (1 g, 0.005 mole) by heating at 100–105° with intimately mixed anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.4 g, 0.0175 mole). The product was decomposed with HCl (1 : 1) and then cooled. The product was collected by filtration and was purified by crystallisation from methanol. Yield of the product was 0.7 g, m.p. 164°, mixed m.p., with IV was undiminished.

6-Acetyl-5-methoxycoumarin was prepared by refluxing 1.5 g, of IV with dimethyl sulphate (1.5 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3.0 g), in acetone (90 ml). The product melted at 115°. (Found : C, 65.97; H, 4.36. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires : C, 66.05; H, 4.62). I.R. band 1742 cm^{-1} and 1724 cm^{-1} (coumarin); 1667 cm^{-1} (ketonic).

6-Ethyl-5-acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin (VI) : 6-Ethyl-5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin¹ (1 g, 0.05 mole) was mixed with acetic anhydride (3 g, .03 mole) and pyridine (2.4 g, .03 mole). The resulting solution, after keeping at room temperature for 24 hr. was poured into crushed ice; solid precipitate was filtered off and on crystallisation from pet-ether gave 1.1 g. of 6-ethyl-5-acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin VI, m.p. 112° (needles). (Found : C, 68.60; H, 5.80. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires : C, 68.24; H, 5.73).

6-Ethyl-5-hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin (VII) : VI (0.5 g, 0.002 mole) was intimately mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.1 g, .008 mole) and was heated at 180° for 1 hr. The reaction product, on decomposition with ice and hydrochloric acid gave a solid precipitate which on purification by crystallisation from methanol gave 0.3 g, of 6-ethyl-5-hydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin VII, m.p. 165° (Found : C, 67.94; H, 5.75. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires : C, 68.24; H, 5.73) I.R. 1724 cm^{-1} (coumarin); 1690 cm^{-1} (ketone).

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